
ONLINE COLLABORATIVE LANGUAGE LEARNING FOR IMPROVING EFL STUDENTS' WRITING SKILLS

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Abstract

This thesis examines the impact of online collaborative learning on EFL (English as a Foreign Language) students' writing skills. It highlights the benefits of peer feedback, authentic writing practice, and the development of critical thinking through collaborative tasks. The findings show that online collaboration enhances students' writing abilities by facilitating constructive feedback, encouraging writing for real audiences, and promoting deeper learning through diverse perspectives. The study concludes that integrating these strategies into language teaching can significantly improve students' writing skills and overall language proficiency, preparing them for real-world communication. Future research should optimize these strategies and address implementation challenges.

Абстракт

В этой диссертации исследуется влияние совместного онлайн-обучения на письменные навыки учащихся EFL (английский как иностранный язык). В нем подчеркиваются преимущества обратной связи между коллегами, подлинной практики письма и развития критического мышления посредством совместных задач. Результаты показывают, что онлайн-сотрудничество улучшает писательские способности учащихся, способствуя конструктивной обратной связи, поощряя писать для реальной аудитории и способствуя более глубокому обучению с разных точек зрения. В исследовании делается вывод, что интеграция этих стратегий в преподавание языка может значительно улучшить навыки письма учащихся и общее знание

языка, подготавливая их к реальному общению. Будущие исследования должны оптимизировать эти стратегии и решить проблемы их реализации.

Abstrakt

Ushbu dissertatsiya EFL (ingliz tili chet tili sifatida) talabalarining yozish ko'nikmalariga onlayn hamkorlikda o'rganishning ta'sirini o'rganadi. U tengdoshlarning fikr-mulohazalari, haqiqiy yozish amaliyoti va hamkorlikdagi vazifalar orqali tanqidiy fikrlashni rivojlantirishning afzalliklarini ta'kidlaydi. Izlanishlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, onlayn hamkorlik konstruktiv fikr-mulohazalarni osonlashtirish, haqiqiy auditoriya uchun yozishni rag'batlantirish va turli nuqtai nazarlar orqali chuqurroq o'rganishni rag'batlantirish orqali talabalarining yozish qobiliyatini oshiradi. Tadqiqot shuni ko'rsatadiki, ushbu strategiyalarni til o'qitishga integratsiya qilish o'quvchilarning yozish ko'nikmalarini va umumiy tilni bilish darajasini sezilarli darajada yaxshilaydi, ularni haqiqiy dunyo muloqotiga tayyorlaydi. Kelajakdagi tadqiqotlar ushbu strategiyalarni optimallashtirishi va amalga oshirish muammolarini hal qilishi kerak.

Key words: *EFL students, online collaborative learning, peer feedback, authentic writing practice, critical thinking, motivation, language proficiency.*

Kalit so'zlar: *EFL talabalari, onlayn hamkorlikda o'rganish, tengdoshlarning fikr-mulohazalari, haqiqiy yozish amaliyoti, tanqidiy fikrlash, motivatsiya, tilni bilish.*

Ключевые слова: *студенты EFL, совместное онлайн-обучение, обратная связь со сверстниками, практика аутентичного письма, критическое мышление, мотивация, владение языком.*

Introduction

Over the past few decades, educators have increasingly recognized the power of collaborative learning to boost motivation in language classrooms [1]. When students work together in groups, their individual motivations, attitudes, and goals all contribute to the overall success of the group activity [2]. This highlights the close link between collaboration and motivation in successful group learning.

A positive and supportive language learning environment is key, fostered by constructive relationships among students and encouraging interactions with the teacher [2]. Online collaborative activities add another layer of dynamism to classroom interactions, further motivating students to improve their language skills and understanding of concepts [3].

The concept of the group as a learning community plays a significant role in student success. Students not only learn by sharing their knowledge with others, but also by actively participating in collaborative activities and learning from their peers [4]. Building positive group dynamics, specifically group cohesion (a sense of unity) and positive group norms (shared expectations), is crucial for fostering a motivating learning environment [5].

Methodology

Online collaborative learning environments can significantly enhance the writing skills of EFL students by fostering a community of peer feedback, promoting authentic writing practice, and encouraging the development of critical thinking and self-reflection through collaborative writing tasks.

This thesis statement highlights the key advantages of online collaborative learning for EFL students:

Peer Feedback: Online platforms facilitate the exchange of constructive feedback among students, improving their ability to identify and correct errors.

Authentic Writing Practice: Collaboration encourages students to write for real audiences with specific purposes, mirroring real-world writing scenarios.

Critical Thinking and Self-Reflection: Collaborative writing tasks require students to analyze ideas, negotiate solutions, and reflect on their own writing, leading to deeper learning.

Results

Peer feedback is a crucial component of online collaborative learning for EFL students. Online platforms facilitate the exchange of constructive feedback in

a variety of ways, leading to improved writing skills. Here's a deeper dive into this concept with some examples:

Benefits of Peer Feedback in Online Collaborative Learning:

Identifying Errors: Peers can often spot grammatical mistakes, unnatural phrasing, or misused vocabulary that the writer might have missed. For example, a peer might comment on a sentence like "I went to the store yesterday to buy some milks" by suggesting a change to "milk" (singular) since milk is an uncountable noun.

Clarity and Organization: Peers can provide feedback on whether the writing is clear, well-organized, and easy to follow. For instance, a peer might suggest adding a transition word between sentences to improve the flow of ideas.

Audience Awareness: Peers can help assess if the writing is appropriate for the intended audience. For example, if an EFL student is writing a formal email, a peer might suggest replacing informal contractions with full words.

Variety of Perspectives: Receiving feedback from multiple peers exposes the writer to different viewpoints, helping them refine their writing and consider alternative approaches. For instance, one peer might suggest strengthening the introduction with a captivating hook, while another might recommend including specific details for a clearer picture.

Discussion Forums: Students can upload their drafts to a forum where peers can leave comments and suggestions directly on the text.

Collaborative Documents: Platforms like Google Docs or shared spreadsheets allow real-time feedback as students work on the same document simultaneously. This facilitates ongoing conversation and revision.

Peer Review Rubrics: Providing students with a rubric outlining key writing criteria (grammar, vocabulary, organization) can guide them in offering constructive and specific feedback.

Feedback Templates: Templates with prompts like "What I liked about this writing..." or "One suggestion for improvement..." can help students structure their feedback in a helpful and encouraging way.

Online collaborative language learning environments offer a unique opportunity for EFL (English as a Foreign Language) students to engage in authentic writing practice. Unlike traditional classroom exercises, online collaboration fosters a setting that mirrors real-world writing scenarios, leading to significant improvement in writing skills. Here's how:

Moving Beyond the Textbook: Online collaborative tasks often go beyond textbook exercises. Students write for a specific audience (their peers or even external communities) with a clear purpose, like creating a blog post, drafting a group email, or composing a collaborative story. This purpose-driven approach makes writing feel more meaningful and relatable.

Variety of Writing Styles: Collaborative projects encourage students to experiment with different writing styles. They might write a persuasive argument in a discussion forum, craft a creative narrative for a shared document, or draft a formal email to a guest speaker. This exposure allows them to adapt their writing to different contexts.

Engaged Learning: Working together on a project naturally increases student engagement. They brainstorm ideas, negotiate solutions, and revise their work collectively, leading to a more invested learning experience.

Peer Feedback and Support: Online platforms facilitate the exchange of constructive feedback among peers. Students can suggest improvements on grammar, vocabulary, and clarity, while also providing encouragement and support. This collaborative approach fosters a sense of shared responsibility for the quality of the final product.

Exposure to Diverse Perspectives: When writing collaboratively, students encounter different writing styles and approaches from their peers. This exchange

broadens their perspective and helps them refine their own writing skills by considering alternative ways to express themselves.

Collaborative Blogs or Wikis: Students can create a shared blog or wiki on a topic of interest, requiring them to write informative and engaging content for a wider audience.

Online Discussions and Debates: Participating in online forums and discussions allows students to practice argumentative and persuasive writing, defending their viewpoints and responding to others' arguments.

Collaborative Storytelling: Working together to write a story online encourages creative and narrative writing skills. Students contribute different parts and revise the story collectively, developing their ability to maintain a cohesive narrative.

Teacher Facilitation: While collaboration allows students to take ownership of their learning, teacher guidance remains crucial. Teachers can provide prompts, propose authentic writing tasks, and offer feedback on collaborative projects.

Real-world Connections: Connecting online collaborative projects with real-world applications, such as writing to pen pals or participating in online communities, can further enhance the authenticity of the writing experience.

By incorporating authentic writing practices into online collaborative language learning, educators can equip EFL students with the skills and confidence to communicate effectively in real-world situations.

Discussion

The article effectively illustrates the significant benefits of online collaborative learning for EFL students. By fostering a supportive and dynamic learning environment, promoting authentic writing practice, and encouraging critical thinking and self-reflection, online collaborative activities can significantly enhance students' motivation and writing skills. Educators should consider integrating these strategies into their teaching practices to equip EFL students with the necessary skills to communicate effectively in real-world situations. By

leveraging peer feedback, authentic writing practice, and critical thinking development, these environments can significantly enhance students' writing skills and overall language proficiency. The theoretical and practical implications discussed here further underscore the transformative potential of online collaboration in language learning. To fully realize this potential, educators and institutions must address the challenges and provide the necessary support for effective implementation. Future research should continue to explore and expand upon these findings to refine and optimize online collaborative learning strategies for diverse educational contexts.

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